

Title: Rebuilding Trust: Countering Social Media Weaponization Through Resilience and Reform

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ABSTRACT

This paper examines the hybrid threats facing American civil society in the digital information space. While the United States focused on counterterrorism efforts in the post-9/11 era, adversarial nations developed and deployed tactics that exploit social and political divisions through digital media. Drawing on contemporary literature this study traces the evolution of modern information warfare within the broader context of hybrid conflicts. Referencing recent conflicts and the strategic use of disinformation, the paper turns to researchers and leaders in the fight against misinformation to identify ways to limit adversary maneuverability in the information domain. The paper concludes by proposing strategic measures to strengthen national resilience, emphasizing the promotion of media literacy programs and civic education among younger generations.

KEYWORDS: hybrid war, unrestricted warfare, like wars, active measures, misinformation, elections, trust, truth decay, Russia

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The modern world is an increasingly complex and confusing place. For many people, the shared underlying truths that bonded our society are being eroded by a sense of cynicism and apathy. While the information revolution has ushered in a new era of global interconnection, individuals are experiencing levels of loneliness that are resulting in deep alienation from our communities and institutions. Even alienation from the concepts of individual self. The multitude of experiences and qualities that make up each individual often contain contradictions that contribute to conflict within the self. A need for universal truth is central to the journey to understand the self and its role in the world.

...the immortal bird of warfare will not be able to attain Nirvana when it is on the verge of decline: When people begin to lean toward and rejoice in the reduced use of military force to resolve conflicts, war will be reborn in another form and in another arena, becoming an instrument of enormous power in the hands of those who harbor intentions of controlling other countries or regions.
– Col. Qiao Liang, “Unrestricted Warfare”

The advent of the internet was marked by a hope of freedom that would create equal opportunity for the pursuit of truth. Now, access to information is defined by social media, tailored to the preferences of its users through an algorithm. Automated algorithms have become the primary means through which people now learn about the world around them. While access to information has granted us the ability to learn a multitude of truths and it contributes to the proliferation of falsehoods. The individual and its relation to information is a critical part of what produces the educated citizens democracy needs to function.

Like many man-made technologies, social media is an extension of ourselves in the digital realm. And like ourselves, is susceptible to a fixation on various base behaviors and emotions that can distort reality and fuel conflict. War and conflict have always been a distinctly

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human endeavor. While they now have expanded into the digital space, they still rely on individual participation and attention. Perhaps even more so than before.

The link between war and politics, as argued by Clausewitz, has always existed. However, participation in conflict is no longer limited to soldiers, politicians, and auxiliary services. Every day people, or non-combatants, are consuming and sharing information that influences public opinion outside the control of traditional authorities. While the concepts of subversion and propaganda are nothing new, this arena presents certain opportunities to malign actors to prey on the weakness of our democracy.

The past decade has seen a development in aggressive electronic and digital warfare capacities by near-peer adversaries such as China and Russia. Recent domestic social and political unrest in the United States has given adversaries the opportunity to utilize and improve their capabilities. From cyberattacks and disinformation to deep fakes and algorithm manipulation, all of these measures are being utilized in a hybrid war against American democracy. These malign actions fall below the threshold of traditional armed conflict, but their impact is strategic and far-reaching.

This paper intends to explore the role that information warfare and social media play in shaping our current domestic political climate, and how foreign adversaries seek to exploit the vulnerabilities inherent in a democracy that relies on an informed and engaged citizenry. By examining recent cases of intentional disinformation and propaganda campaigns from bad actors, this paper aims to understand how these tactics are being used offensively against our communities and how we can begin to build meaningful defenses in response.

Hybrid War

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The asymmetric nature of conflict in the twenty-first century has been extensively studied over the past two decades. Concepts such as fifth-generation warfare, hybrid warfare, and gray-zone operations have emerged to describe the increasingly complex and ambiguous nature of modern conflict. While many scholars have attempted to define these phenomena as it continues to unfold, the experiences of combat leaders who have faced new challenges in unfamiliar environments, begs us to ask the question: How often does strategy built on theory and assumption succeed in novel environments with fundamentally different variables? How can we confront threats which we do not yet fully understand?

As Sun Tzu observed, "Know the enemy and know yourself, and you need not fear the result of a hundred battles." The challenge now is that the "enemy" is often shapeshifting, invisible, or embedded within one's own society. To answer these questions, scholars and strategists alike must examine our adversaries' perspectives and motivations which have led them to adopt asymmetric tactics.

Unrestricted Warfare, published by PLA colonels Qiao Liang and Wang Xiangsui, offers great insight into the perspectives near peer adversaries as they also work to understand the strategic realities of the modern world. They describe a new battlefield that is categorized by the need to use "all means, including armed force or non-armed force, military and non-military, and lethal and non-lethal means to compel the enemy to accept one's interests." They outline areas of operation in which a state can wield influence against an adversary. Their intended opponent in this piece of revolutionary military thought was, of course, the United States.

The philosophy can be encapsulated in the idea that in modern warfare there are no rules, all of society is now a battlefield. A future conflict would inevitably encompass attacks on all elements of society: financial, political, media, healthcare, digital infrastructure, etc. *Unrestricted*

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Warfare holds a mirror up to an open society like the United States, describing its vulnerabilities in detail and outlining a strategy to exploit them through non-traditional, asymmetric means that blur the line between war and peace.

In this new conflict, adversaries will explore the United State's vulnerabilities rather than engage in military confrontations. Social and political cleavages will be exacerbated to create greater division through actions targeting our nation's digital infrastructure, manipulation of public opinion, and undermining of institutions.

Many of the hybrid warfare or gray-zone capabilities outlined in *Unrestricted Warfare* were not unconceivable at the time of publishing. Economic sanctions, legal sanctions, and diplomatic pressure were tactics that states had been using to compete with each other for centuries. However, the authors could not have predicted how social media would be utilized as an offensive capability. Interestingly enough, the Russian intelligence services became a core innovator when it came to applying new technologies to offensive gray-zone tactics.

States that do not possess the capabilities or political capital to engage directly in conventional military operations against adversaries developed these asymmetric strategies out of necessity. Russia, like China, has been operating under similar assumptions about the nature of modern interstate conflict. After the invasion of Crimea, Western journalists reported a new "Gerasimov Doctrine" that outlined a Russian interpretation of hybrid warfare in which old school Soviet subversion tactics found a new life in the age of information warfare. Foreign adversaries have been developing these capabilities for decades and our national security apparatus has only recently begun to recognize and respond to these threats.

Like Wars

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Of all the technological innovations of the past two decades, the advent of social media has had the most profound impact on how people perceive and engage with the world around them. As with many groundbreaking inventions, the unintended consequences of such a powerful communication tool could never have been fully anticipated, even by its creators. Today, we are faced with the sobering reality that many of our systems can be weaponized by those seeking to spread malign influence and sow division within society.

Recent events have demonstrated how social media can be harnessed by populations to share political information and even challenge or overthrow governments. The Arab Spring and the Hong Kong protests illustrated the power and utility of these platforms. Social media offered oppressed populations a tool to organize, communicate, and take agency over their own circumstances.

While the ability to influence and mobilize people at an individual level was revolutionary, these developments did not go unnoticed. When some viewed it as a force for democratic empowerment, others saw an opportunity to exploit the same mechanisms for their own purposes. Doors were opened that could not be closed.

The Cold War was characterized by an intensive use of information influence operations as alternative to direct confrontation between the world powers. The tactics and tradecraft that emerged as a consequence of these parameters defined the future of interstate espionage, even as it moved towards the digital age. To better understand these developments, it is worth defining old and new concepts such as “active measures” and “sock puppets” to describe current efforts to engage in information warfare.

What we today refer to as “disinformation campaigns” were once known as “active measures” in Soviet intelligence circles. These actions incorporated previous strategies of

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political warfare and propaganda into vast undertakings by modern bureaucratic intelligence services. The Soviet's active disinformation operations served to exacerbate existing tensions and contradictions within the adversary's body politic, by leveraging facts, fakes, into a disorienting mix against their adversaries. Applying these tactics in the digital age created an effect where a once slow-moving, highly intensive process quickly became rapid and far more difficult to trace.

Through modern media, active measures and disinformation threaten the integrity of our democracy on a daily basis. In recent years, "sock puppets" or social media accounts that pose as front for modern propaganda operators, have been found across the internet, especially on sites like Facebook. These accounts follow classic Cold War active measures by targeting the extremes of both sides of American politics to create internal division.

Through federal investigation it was found that the Russian government had created an entire agency dedicated to this new form of information warfare called the Information Research Agency. The agency played a role in shaping the narrative around the 2016 presidential elections, in which there was an unprecedented environment of domestic division, conflict and controversy. Internal divisions that had been stirring deep within American society became an open wound for the international community to see, creating a target rich environment for Russian hackers and trolls.

In this environment, rather than government officials or politicians, internet users became targets of renewed cold war tactics. As tensions between Russia and the United States have increased, online public discourse became a new battlefield in which Russia could manipulate public perception, increase volatility, and exacerbate division within the American political system.

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Case Studies

America once again found itself confronted by the threat of foreign interference through malicious acts of digital sabotage, espionage, and disinformation at the hands of Russian state actors. Events in countries within Russia's strategic sphere of influence had long foreshadowed such tactics. To those paying attention, it should not have been a surprise. Since the Cold War, Russian intelligence operations have consistently sought to exploit internal divisions within targeted states as a means to influence and destabilize. Ukraine was no exception.

The events in Ukraine in 2014 demonstrated the effectiveness of Russian digital influence operations. Through a coordinated blend of cyberattacks, social media propaganda, and state-backed media messaging, Russia was able to confuse public perception and undermine trust in Ukrainian institutions, all in order to justify the annexation of Crimea. Russia's later attempts to interfere in Ukraine's 2014 presidential election highlight how modern conflict increasingly moves between digital tools and physical force.

Active Measures by Thomas Rid covers the well documented case of social media engineering by Russian intelligence unit GRU. According to the agency's internal reporting, GRU created multiple Facebook groups with the intention of stirring up negative feelings about the government in Kyiv. These active measures were done in order to promote pro-Crimean independence narratives and to alienate the Crimean population from pro-Western parties and organizations.

On March 12, 2014, GRU attempted to use old-school Soviet tactics by forging fake emails and leaking them to create controversy. These forged emails were designed to suggest that the Ukrainian Euromaiden revolution was a Western plot orchestrated by the CIA. The narrative GRU was attempting to establish was that the CIA was recruiting far-right extremists

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for covert military operations. The letters were used to support the Kremlin's claims that any Western aligned parties or movements in Ukraine were Nazi influenced. Then, as Eastern Ukraine descended into civil war, the intensity and frequency of Russian operations targeting infrastructure increased ahead of the Ukrainian presidential election. In the eastern regions, voting software was repeatedly disrupted by cyberattacks, and election board members faced threats as they prepared for the vote.

The invasion of Ukraine is the latest among many offensive military actions taken by Russia in the last two decades. The interventions in Moldova and Georgia reflect Russia's strategy of projecting power in its sphere of influence, targeting smaller states whose divisions make them vulnerable to external manipulation. By exploiting ethnic tensions, political instability, and energy dependence, Russia has systematically undermined the sovereignty of neighboring countries to maintain regional dominance. These developments illustrate a calculated grand strategy by the Kremlin, compelling Western observers to reflect on the deeper strategic intent behind Putin's claim that the fall of the Soviet Union was "the greatest geopolitical catastrophe of the 20th century."

These tactics have not only targeted our allies abroad, but also our institutions at home. In the months following the 2016 Presidential Election, Americans were exposed to the idea that even our own democratic processes could be subject to foreign influence operations. The idea that a foreign intelligence service could penetrate and influence our institutions was unprecedented and deeply alarming. The U.S. intelligence community published a report detailing the scope and magnitude of Russia's interference efforts.

The report noted that the tactics used during the 2016 election mirrored those employed by Russia to undermine former Soviet republics. It also reported similarities to the methods used

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by the Internet Research Agency to advance pro-Russian narratives in Ukraine. The primary conclusion of the report was that Vladimir Putin himself ordered the interference in the presidential election. The IC found evidence of the execution of a coherent and aggressive campaign to undermine public faith in the US democratic process, denigrate Secretary Clinton, and harm her electability and potential presidency.

Truth Decay

Open societies do not support only one conception of “truth”, they rather seek to establish laws and institutions, enabling people with divergent views to live together in peace.
- Karl Popper

Following the Second World War, scholars and commentators examined why democratic nations were able to engage in total war and remain unified in the face of existential threats. At a fundamental level, consent of the governed and social cohesion empowered war time leaders to act decisively and effectively to attain victory. However, the attributes democratic societies possessed to fight and win wars, such as reliance on public opinion, and civilian oversight of the military, have become potential vulnerabilities to exploitation through the asymmetric tactics employed by our adversaries.

In many ways, America’s greatest vulnerability is itself. Our polarization, our racial tensions, our decentralized media ecosystem are all fertile ground for narrative warfare. These vulnerabilities must be addressed through a whole of society response that properly assesses and ascertains potential solutions. A useful term to understand these vulnerabilities to disinformation is “truth decay,” as described in a RAND Corporation report of the same name. This concept

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helps frame how a declining trust in facts, institutions, and objective information contributes to the erosion of national resilience.

In the report, RAND offers an approach to combating the effects of truth decay and disinformation. These solutions are valuable to those attempting to address information threats from adversarial states in the “post truth” media landscape. RAND systematizes the process of truth decay by identifying its drivers and social repercussions. The decentralization of media combined with increased political polarization and the intentional spread of disinformation results in trends of increased disagreement of facts, a blurring between what is fact and opinion, the prevalence of opinion over facts in media, and a declining trust in traditional sources of information. This results in a breakdown of civil discourse, alienation, and political dysfunction.

The truth decay process describes the conditions that have led to a post-truth environment in American politics and media. In the report, RAND posits that solutions for truth decay must be a whole of society effort that requires multiple disciplines to engage citizens on the individual level. An intervention in education to promote civic life, tools to support media literacy, and government transparency will be required to revitalize America’s civic infrastructure.

Alienation and disengagement from civic institutions pose a serious threat to our democracy. However, trust in these institutions can be rebuilt over time through deliberate civic engagement and sustained public effort. As the Nation develops a defense against weaponized information, education should be seen as a key part of our collective civil defense.

Policy makers must look towards the example set by our allies in this struggle we share when faced with disinformation measures from Russia. NATO’s newest ally, Finland, is on the frontline of this digital conflict. Finland has consistently held the top spot in European media literacy rankings since measurements began in 2017 and has been a leader in the European

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response to misinformation. The 2014 Russian influence operations in Ukraine and Crimea, prompted Finland to begin developing a whole of government approach to combating misinformation. That same year, as Finland was in the midst of national and European elections, experts observed an increase in Russian propaganda, medical disinformation, and other misleading digital content. These findings provoked a distinct response from Finnish civil society, governmental and non-governmental organizations working in concert to combat misinformation.

Independent fact-checker group Faktabaari began to strengthen a defense by providing fact-checking services and information to the Finnish public. However, while the effort was sustained, it did not provide the desired level of impact. Faktabaari determined that it would be more effective to educate people to become their own “fact-checkers” of misinformation through digital media literacy programs. Since then, Finnish and European experts have developed a robust network of non-governmental and civil society organizations across the continent whose mission is to study and combat misinformation.

The Finnish approach to establishing effective organizations must be understood by American policy makers as it is already being replicated in other European states. While it might seem as if a country such as Finland would engage in a concentrated level of centralized planning when it comes to national education, these media literacy programs are an exception. The Finnish National Agency for Education develops the national educational curriculum, however individual communities and their teachers are left to determine their own lesson plans. In addition to NGOs such as Faktabaari, government organizations such as the Finnish National Audio Visual Institute (KAVI) are responsible for developing the national curriculum for media

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literacy. These programs were quickly implemented after the threat of misinformation and Russian disinformation became apparent.

Overall, the media literacy campaigns in Finland have been successful and have been exported to other European education systems in order to measure their effectiveness elsewhere. Even here in the U.S. a study was conducted with high-schoolers and found that just a half-dozen 50-minute lessons could help students demonstrate appropriate skepticism of digital media. As these programs demonstrate their effectiveness, they must be thoughtfully adapted to the cultural and organizational contexts in which they are implemented. The United States, for instance, differs significantly from Finland in both structure and societal norms.

Resources developed by civil society groups and government organizations are left to be implemented at the discretion of Finland's teachers. In Finland, however, all primary and secondary educators are required to have a master's degree. This provides a level of expertise on the research process and information to the classroom that is not expected in the professional standards of the United States. For that reason, implementing this approach in the United States could be challenging. Any similar initiative in the U.S. may be required to be at the direction of the federal government and the Department of Education, rather than from the community level.

Any conversation on proposing a solution to combat malign information campaigns for foreign adversaries is also a conversation about combatting disinformation. While European models are practical for European societies, models for the U.S. may be quite different. Americans tend to distrust directives from high authorities such as the federal government so a mandatory curriculum may not be optimal. This is where the Finnish model may get it right, leaving discretion to school districts and teachers. However, post-COVID narratives surrounding

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misinformation have been very politicized in the U.S., potentially hindering the effectiveness of any public messaging or efforts to educate the American public.

Conclusion

In order to build meaningful defenses against measured influence operations that target the security of our democratic institutions, policy makers must incorporate the concepts presented by RAND, as well as lessons learned from European allies. Any forward facing solution must in part engage the younger Americans who are more familiar with the digital media ecosystem than past generations, as well as school-age Americans who are still learning to navigate the complex online platforms. An intervention into primary school education concerning civic education, the role of media, as well as a media literacy curriculum aimed at informing students about misinformation would be meaningful first steps in constructing societal resilience to adversarial influence operations.

The cornerstone of a healthy democracy is a well educated citizenry. If Americans can be made aware of how both intentional and unintentional misinformation distort discourse, then a renewed sense of ownership over our public square, institutions, and democratic way of life becomes possible. Aristotle's concept of the ideal educated citizen remains as relevant today as ever. Our society requires individuals that have the moral and civic integrity to take responsibility for their communities and improve them for the better. We must reengage Americans in the values of a civic education, focusing on media literacy to protect our communities against the drift towards disengagement.

To combat the symptoms of truth decay and misinformation is, in effect, to deny adversaries the informational maneuverability they rely on to exploit societal divisions and

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undermine public trust. This can only be achieved through education and ownership. Without an educated and engaged citizenry, democracy risks dysfunction and the collapse of government truly rooted in the people. Modern life in all its complexities presents an uncertain path forward. However, as with many things, the fundamentals never change.